

Development And Characterization of Niosomal Buccal Film for Hyperlipidemia

Neha D. Naringe*, Dimpal Sarkar, Pankaj Dhapke, Nitin Padole, Nilakshi Dhoble, Jagdish R. Baheti

Department of Pharmaceutics, Kamla Nehru College of Pharmacy Butibori, RTMNU Nagpur Maharashtra (India)-441108

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ABSTRACT: Atypically high blood levels of any or all lipids or lipoproteins as a result of aberrant fat metabolism or function are known as hyperlipidemia. the primary causes of heart attacks, ischemic heart disease (IHD), cardiovascular disorders, and atherosclerosis, among others. Both main and secondary factors can cause hyperlipidemia, which is regarded as a chronic condition whose symptoms can be managed with anti-hyperlipidemia medications. The goal is to create lovastatin niosomes in order to increase the drug's bioavailability. The application of preformulation parameters optimizes the quality of the drug product while increasing the likelihood of obtaining a formulation that is safe, effective, and stable. FTIR, DSC, and UV spectroscopy were used in the pre-formulation investigation to identify the API. According to published research, the drug has low solubility and bioavailability. Therefore, we created lipid-based nanoparticles, or niosomes, to improve the drug's permeability, solubility, and bioavailability. Compared to other nanoparticles, niosomes offer additional benefits. Lovastatin-loaded The Rotatory Evaporation Method was used to create the niosomes, and a Box Behnken design was used for optimization. For oral ingestion, a thin layer formed in a round-bottom flask and was hydrated using phosphate buffer 6.8 pH. A hazy (milky) niosomal solution developed following hydration. The optimized batch B9 had a particle size of 209.2 nm, a PDI of 2.697, and an entrapment effectiveness of 95.55%.

Keyword: Hyperlipidemia, atherosclerosis, nanoparticles, niosomes, buccal delivery.

1. INTRODUCTION:

The oral route is the important route of drug administration for various treatments but having some limitation,[1] such as drug degradation, poor absorption, stability issues and low solubility, thus there is need to develop novel dosages form for overcoming limitation.[2] Currently research going on novel development and how will improve potential activity of drug. Hyperlipidemia is a condition of abnormally levels of lipids or lipoproteins in the blood due to abnormal fat metabolism or function,[3] and it is caused by dietary disorders, obesity, genetic diseases such as familial hypercholesterolemia (FH) or other diseases such as diabetes. Patients with hyperlipidemia are about twice as likely to develop cardiovascular disease (CVD). [4,5] classification of hyperlipidemia based on the causes, i.e. Primary (genetic factor) and secondary hyperlipidemia (external factor). [6]

Statin antihyperlipidemic drug is useful in the treatment of hyperlipidemia. [7,8] Lovastatin is a widely prescribed statin that effectively lowers LDL cholesterol, [9] yet its clinical utility is hampered by poor oral bioavailability ($\sim 5\%$) due to low solubility, extensive gastrointestinal degradation, and first-pass hepatic metabolism. Lovastatin belongs to BCS Class-II, which shows low aqueous solubility and high permeability as per IP. Moreover, its absorption through the oral route is very poor. Solubility is the major obstacle to complete drug dissolution in the intestinal fluids. Lovastatin incorporated into niosomes to increasing solubility and bioavailability also, administrated buccally due to high permeability. [10]

In Buccal drug delivery, drug is directly administrated to buccal mucosa and enter into systemic circulation and bypassing first-pass effects. [11] Buccal film prepared with polymer [12], plasticizer [13], surfactant [14], solvent [15], flavouring agent [16], sweetening agent etc, [17,18] buccal film often suffer from adhesion, release, drug mixing in saliva and limited permeability, which compromise their therapeutic potential. [19] In this context, niosomes is a vesicular carriers made from non-ionic surfactants (eg Span and Tween) and cholesterol (sterod)[20] by Hand Shaking method,[21]offer a stable, easily degradable and form encapsulate between drug and carrier, that entrapped both hydrophilic and lipophilic compounds, prevent against degradation, and provide controlled release.[22] The study aims to improve lovastatin bioavailability, prolong systemic exposure, and enhance therapeutic efficacy in hyperlipidemia management thereby satisfying the urgent need for alternative, non-invasive, and more effective statin delivery modalities.

2. METHODS AND MATERIALS

Lovastatin was purchased from b. l. chemical products pvt. ltd mumbai, india. Span 60 and HPMC K4M obtained from oba chemie pvt. ltd. And Cholesterol are obtained from research lab fine chem industries, mumbai. Poly Ethylene Glycol 400 and citric acid is received from Sisco chem lab Pvt. Ltd. Sodium Starch Glycolate is obtained from loba chemie pvt. ltd. All organic solvents and the other chemicals is in analytical grade.

2.1 Preformulation study

Drug identification can be confirmed by performing different methods like solubility, UV Spectroscopy, DSC and Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR) drug-excipient compatibility study.

1. Solubility

Take a small amount of the drug Lovastatin and add it to the 10ml solution like methanol, phosphate butter, and distilled water until it reaches to supersaturated solution. The supersaturated solution was then kept in the centrifuge for 15-30 min. Take the supernatant from the solution and evaluate it by using a UV spectrophotometer. Three determinations were carried out for each sample to calculate the solubility of the drug.[23]

2. UV Spectroscopy

10mg of Lovastatin was dissolved in 2-3ml of methanol then makeup to 10ml with methanol & 6.8 pH buffer so as to get a stock solution of 1000 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ concentration. From the above stock solution subsequent dilutions were made using 6.8pH buffer to get the concentration of 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ concentration and was scanned under UV Spectroscopy between 200-400nm ranges.(Shimadzu UV1800) [24]

3. Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC)

Thermal behavior of Lavastatin formulations were studied using differential scanning calorimetry (DSC). In aluminum pans, 5 mg samples were heated at a scanning rate of 10 $^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$ at 40–200 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ under a nitrogen flow of 50 mL/min. [25]

4. Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FT-IR)

The physical properties of the physical assortment were comparing with those of lovastatin pure drug. Samples were assorted comprehensively through 100mg potassium bromide IR powder as well as compacted under vacuum at a pressure of concerning 12 psi for 3 minutes. The ensuing disc was mounted in an appropriate holder in Brukers Alpha IR spectrophotometer and the IR spectrum was recorded from 3500 cm^{-1} to 500 cm^{-1} . The resultant spectrum was compared for any spectrum changes. [26]

5. Drug Polymer Compatibility Study

FTIR spectra of pure lovastatin & physical mixture (Lovastatin + Cholesterol + Span 60) was recorded. Around 1:1 ratio of sample, and then the sample was analysed over wave numbers ranging from 4000 - 400 cm^{-1} at transmission mode.[27]

2.2 Preparation of Niosomes

Niosomal formulation was carried out by the “Rotatory Evaporation Method ” by using “Rotatory Evaporator apparatus.”Drug, non-ionic surfactant, cholesterol are dissolved in organic solvent, Remove organic solvent at 60 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 110 rpm form a dried thin layer film, dried thin layer film hydrated with phosphate buffer pH 6.8 and formed a niosome suspension. [28,29] The design expert was used to optimize niosomal formulation using cholesterol, Span 60, and sonication time as variables. Eleven batches were prepared (Box Behnken design) and analyzed for particle size and entrapment efficiency.[30]

Table No. 1: Variables in the design to prepare niosomes with decoded values and constraints

Independent variables (Factors)	Low value	High value	Dependent variables (Response)
X ₁ = Cholesterol (mg)	50	100	Y ₁ = Particle size
X ₂ =Span 60 (mg)	100	150	Y ₂ = Entrapment efficacy
X ₃ = Sonication time (min)	5	10	Y ₃ = Zeta potential

- 1. Particle size and zeta potential:** The hydrodynamic diameter, size distribution and zeta potential (ZP) of the prepared niosomes were determined by Litesizer (BCOP, Nagpur). Before performing the measurements, the formulations were diluted 100 times with deionized water and mixed thoroughly, and then measurements were done in triplicate at $25 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ with a scattering light angle of 90° . [31]
- 2. Encapsulation efficiency:** The untrapped drug was separated by centrifugation in a cooling centrifuge at 10,000 rpm and at 4 C for 1 hour. After centrifugation, the supernatant was separated and diluted with methanol: phosphate buffer 6.8 pH ratio. The absorbance was measured using UV spectrophotometer at λ max. [32,33]

The drug entrapping efficiency was determined by using the following equation:

$$\% \text{Entrapment efficiency} = \frac{\text{Total amount of drug} - \text{amount of free drug}}{\text{Total amount of drug}} \times 100$$

- 3. Field Emission Scanning electron microscopy (FE-SEM):** The cross-sectional morphologies of the fabricated nano-active packaging films were observed using Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscope (FE-SEM). Dried NAP films were dipped in liquid nitrogen and then cracked with the help of tweezers. A small section of cracked NAP was fixed on conductive SEM stubs with double-sided tape and coated with carbon. FE-SEM was operated at an accelerated voltage of 10 kV. [34]

2.3 Preparation of lovastatin niosomes loaded buccal film

Lovastatin niosomes loaded buccal film prepared by solvent casting method using film former (VJ). Generally, film former polymer, plasticizer, disintegrating agent, permeation enhancer, pH adjuster used in the preparation of film such as HPMC E15, PEG-400, SSG, Citric acid, Distilled water etc [35,36]

Evaluation of Niosomes Loaded Buccal Film

- 1. Average weight of the film:** Weight variation of the prepared films was studied by individually weighing 10 randomly selected patches. Such determination was performed for each formulation and calculated the average weight of film. [37]
- 2. Weight variation of the film:** The weight variations of prepared rapidly dissolving films were determined to ensure the homogeneity of the film. This was conducted by cutting the films into squares (2×2 cm). The individual weight of 3 pieces was recorded using digital balance. [38,39]
- 3. Surface PH:** The surface pH of the prepared films ranged from 6.5 to 6.8. This range is close to neutrality and compatible to the buccal pH. Therefore, the prepared films are expected to not cause any irritation to buccal mucosa. [40]
- 4. Thickness measurement:** Thickness of each film was measured using Vernier caliper held at 3 different positions on the films and the average was calculated. [41]
- 5. Drug content:** The drug content was determined by cutting the area of oral film 4cm^2 and dissolved in phosphate buffer pH 6.8 in a 10ml volumetric flask. Absorbance of the solution was taken at 237 nm by using UV spectrophotometer (Shimazu UV1800) [42]
- 6. Folding endurance:** Folding endurance was determined by repeatedly folding a small strip of patches (approximately 2×2 cm) at the same place till it broke. The number of times patches could be folded at the same place, without breaking gave the value of folding endurance and it was recorded. [43]
- 7. Disintegration study:** The disintegration time was performed by placing the film in a beaker containing 25 ml of water. It was stirred at every 10 sec time intervals. The time required for the film to disintegrate was recorded. [44]
- 8. Percentage Moisture contents:** % Moisture contents of the film are calculated by finding the difference between the weights measured initially prior to the placement of film in the desiccators and after specific time interval. Calcium chloride is placed in the desicator and the whole apparatus is kept for 24 h. Following equation is used to measure the % moisture uptake. [45]

$$\% \text{ Moisture content} = \frac{\text{initial weight} - \text{final weight}}{\text{final weight}} \times 100$$

9. *In-vitro* dissolution study: Dissolution tests are performed with the basket method USP 1 or IP 2 at rotational speeds of 50 rpm using a Electrolab dissolution apparatus (TDT08-LL). The dissolution medium is 250mL of bi-distilled water or simulated saliva solution, pH 6.8, Temperature is kept at 37 ± 1 °C. Sample solution (5mL) is withdrawn at appropriate time intervals (1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 8, 10, 12, 14, 15, 20, 30min) and the drawn volume is replaced with blank dissolution medium, also kept at 37 ± 1 °C, absorbance is measured by UV/Visible spectrophotometer at 237 nm. [46]

10. *In-vitro* permeation: In vitro diffusion study was performed by using modified franz diffusion cell across cellophane membrane. Phosphate buffer solution (PBS) of pH6.8 was used as medium for diffusion study. Buccal filmes of dimension 2x2 cm² were placed on the membrane, which was placed between donor and receptor compartments of Franz diffusion cell. Cellophane membrane was brought in contact with PBS of pH 6.8 filled in receptor compartment. Temperature was maintained at 37 °C with stirring at 50 rpm using a magnetic bead stirrer. 1ml of sample was withdrawn from a receptor compartment at pre-determined interval and was replaced with fresh PBS of pH 6.8. With suitable dilution, samples were measured for absorbance at 200-400 nm using UV visible spectrophotometer. [47]

2.4 Stability study of the finally selected batch:

Q1A (R2) guideline and defines the stability data package for a new drug substance or drug product that is sufficient for a registration application within the three regions of the EC, Japan, and the United States. It does not seek necessarily to cover the testing for registration in or export to other areas of the world.

The purpose of stability testing is to provide evidence on how the quality of a drug substance or drug product varies with time under the influence of a variety of environmental factors such as temperature, humidity, and light, and to establish a re-test period for the drug substance or shelf life for the drug product and recommended storage conditions. [48]

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Organoleptic properties: Organoleptic properties were examined visually with naked eyes for the preliminary identification of the drug.

Table No.2: Organoleptic properties of Lovastatin

Sr. No.	Parameters	Properties
1	Colour	White in colour
2	Odour	Odourless
3	State	Crystalline powder

UV Spectroscopy: The UV spectrophotometry was performed in methanol: phosphate buffer(6.8pH) ratio, Maximum wavelength (max) is specific for every drug substance, and it is also one of the identification criteria. The maximum absorbances is for Lovastatin drug taken in Methanol: phosphate buffer pH 6.8 ratio at λ max 237 as shown in table,

Fig No.1: UV spectrum of Lovastatin in methanol: phosphate buffer pH 6.8

Table No.3: Calibration curve of Lovastatin in methanol: phosphate buffer pH 6.8

Sr. No.	Concentration (µg/ml)	Absorbance
1	2	0.406
2	4	0.478
3	6	0.523
4	8	0.589
5	10	0.617
6	12	0.689

Fig No.2: UV spectrum and Standard Calibration curve of Lovastatin in methanol: phosphate buffer pH 6.8

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC)

DSC is used to study the thermal behavior of Lovastatin used in the niosomes as well as to detect phase transitions like melting and crystallization. The DSC thermogram (Fig.) revealed sharp endothermic peaks at 171.91°C, which represent the corresponding melting temperature of lovastatin, respectively.

Fig No.3: DSC Graph of Lovastatin drug

Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy

Fig No.4: FT-IR spectrum of Lovastatin+ span 60+cholesterol

Table No.4: Reported and Observed peak of Lovastatin and Lovastatin+ span 60+ cholesterol IR spectra

Characteristic Functional Group	Standard Value (cm ⁻¹)	Lovastatin+ span 60+ cholesterol
C=O (Ketone)	1705-1725	1712.88
C-O	1275-1200	1206.58
C-H	2850-2975	2922.31
-OH (free)	3400-3700	-
C=C	1475-1600	-
C-H (-CH ₃ bend)	1450 and 1375	1451.88
C-H (alkenes-out of plane bend)	650-1000	1049.69

The FTIR spectrum shows characteristic peaks near standard values, indicating no major shifts. This confirms no incompatibility between drug and excipients, proving compatibility in the formulation.

Formulation development and optimization

Optimization of the concentration of cholesterol, span 60 and sonication time by design state case design expert software (version 13)

Table No.5: Box Behnken design batches composition and characterization

Formulation code	Independent factor			Dependent factor		
	(X ₁)	(X ₂)	(X ₃)	(Y ₁)	(Y ₂)	(Y ₃)
N1	75	125	45	329	91.6	-39
N2	100	125	30	415.42	88.59	-39.68
N3	75	100	30	375.48	92.45	-40.03
N4	75	100	60	256.46	92.53	-43.97
N5	100	150	45	402.16	87.5	-38.38
N6	50	125	60	212.89	94.78	-41.47
N7	50	150	45	294.34	93.66	-39.2
N8	75	150	30	350.2	90.69	-38.31
N9	50	100	45	209.2	95.55	-42.3
N10	100	100	45	400.16	87.23	-41
N11	75	150	60	321.25	89	-35

The independent variables selected to optimize the niosomes were cholesterol (X₁, mg), Span 60 (X₂, mg), and sonication time (X₃, min) with their low, medium, and high levels. The dependent variables were particle size (Y₁, nm) entrapment efficacy (%), and Zeta Potential.

Fig No.5: Contour plot and 3D plot of particle size

Fig No.6: Contour plot and 3D plot of Entrapment efficiency

Fig No.7: Contour plot and 3D plot Zeta potential of Zeta Potential

Evaluation of Niosomes

Particle size and zeta potential

Fig No.8: Particle size and zeta potential of niosomes

Field Scanning electron microscopy (SEM)

Fig No.9: FE-SEM of Lovastatin- loaded niosomes

The FE-SEM range of Niosomes of lovastatin shows that niosomes was spherical & size distribution around the 200-500 nm range.

Formulation Design

Niosomal Buccal film was prepared using various concentration of formulation code.

Table No.6: Formulation Design of Niosomes Loaded Buccal film

Composition	Formulation code					
	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6
Niosomes equivalent to 10 mg lovastatin/film	120	120	120	120	120	120
HPMC K4M (mg)	100	300	600	450	650	700
PEG-400 (ml)	2	2	2	2	2	2
SSG (mg)	20	20	20	20	20	20
Citric acid (mg)	5	5	5	5	5	5
Dichloromethane: Ethanol (ml)	10	10	10	10	10	10

Evaluation of Niosomes Loaded Buccal Film

- Physical appearances:** The Formulated niosomal film were found to be clear, smooth, uniform, flexible, and transparent appearances.
- Average weight:** The average weight of 10 film was calculated using a digital weighing balance The average weight of all niosomal films was shown in table no.7, range is in between 41.6 and 60 mg.
- Weight variation:** Three film weight was calculated using a digital balance in weight variation, The weight variation of all niosomal films was provided in table no.7, The Niosomal film is in the 47.2 and 62.6 mg.
- Thickness:** The thickness of the niosomal buccal films was measured using Vernier calliper. The thickness of the niosomal films prepared with HPMC K4M respectively, Thickness of niosomal buccal films were found between 0.22-0.39 mm.
- Surface pH of film:** The surface pH was noted by Digital pH meter near the surface of niosomal buccal films and allowing to equilibrate for 1 min and the surface pit of all niosomal buccal films was given in table no.7, The surface pH of the niosomal buccal films was found to in between pH 6.77-6.94.

- 6. Folding Endurance of niosomal films:** The folding endurance of the niosomal films was determined by repeatedly folding a small strip of the niosomal films at the same place till it broke and the average folding endurance of all niosomal films was given in table no.7, The folding endurance average ranges between 7.3-12.2.

Table No.7: Evolution parameter of F1 to F6 batches

Batch	Average weight (mg)	Weight variation (mg)	Thickness (mm)	Surface pH	Folding endurances	% Moisture content (%)
F1	41.6±1.08	47.2±4.04	0.22 ±0.4	6.94±0.05	7.33±1.42	2.03±0.15
F2	47.3±0.57	49.2±1.60	0.26±0.7	6.79±0.04	9.6±0.8	2.13±0.3
F3	55.8±0.8	56.3±2.64	0.33±0.02	6.88±0.03	11.6±1.08	2.4±0.14
F4	52.6±0.3	52±2.54	0.30±0.05	6.77±0.21	10.6±1.15	2.22±0.3
F5	57.1±1.23	57.33±1.52	0.37±0.03	6.84±0.12	11.8±1.4	2.52±0.8
F6	60±1.75	62.66±2.51	0.39±0.4	6.85±0.13	12.2±0.7	2.57±0.31

- 7. Percentage moisture content:** All the batches have minimum moisture content showed least percentage moisture content in all batches. The Percentage moisture content studies carried in a desiccator containing anhydrous calcium chloride. The percentage moisture content is minimum for F3 is 2.4, because the concentration of the polymers and disintegrating agent. The percentage of moisture content was calculated as the difference between initial and final weight with respect to final weight.
- 8. Disintegration time of niosomal films:** Film of 2 x 2 cm² size taken and disintegration time checked visually. In each case three niosomal films were used and the average disintegration time was Calculated; the results were shown in table no.8.
- 9. Drug Content uniformity of niosomal films:** From each batch, film was selected and drug content was determined thrice and average was noted. The results were shown in table no.8. The drug was uniformly dispersed in all niosomal films. The S.D. value calculated for such formulation is very less which suggest that the results are reproducible and accuracy in the method used to prepare the niosomal films.

Table No.8: Evolution parameter of F1 to F6 batches

Batch	Disintegration Time (sec)	Drug Content (%)
F1	27.6±1.9	93.41±1.35
F2	28.3±1.3	91.04±1.21
F3	28.9±0.57	96.82±0.7
F4	28.66±1.4	94.68±1.03
F5	29.85±0.92	95.19±0.6
F6	30±1	96.87±0.53

10. *In-vitro* drug release

Fig No.10: *In vitro* dissolution profile for niosomal buccal film of Lovastatin

The figure shows that all Lovastatin niosomal buccal films (F1–F6) released the drug quickly, with F3 showing the highest release (94% in 7 hr). Low standard deviations confirm result consistency, and F3 was the most effective.

11. *In vitro* Permeation study:

Fig No.11: *In vitro* dissolution profile for niosomal buccal film of Lovastatin

All six buccal film formulations release lovastatin rapidly and continuously over 10 minutes, with F3 showing the fastest and highest permeation about ~94.4%. F1–F3 deliver a good permeated and greater cumulative releases.

CONCLUSION

The research work was development of niosomal buccal film of lovastatin for potentiating anti-hyperlipidemia activity. Niosomes were successfully formulated by rotatory evaporation techniques & optimized by using 3³ factorial design, N9 batch was optimized with high entrapment efficiency 95.55%, particle size 209.2 nm & zeta potential -42.3mV. Optimized batch of niosomes was centrifuges and entrapped drug used in preparation of buccal film by solvent casting method, after the formulation and evaluation of niosomes loaded buccal film, the F3 batch were optimized by drug content (96.8% content), rapid disintegration time (approximately 28.9 seconds) and minimal moisture uptake (2.4%). Niosomal buccal film could be one of the alternative approaches to other drug delivery systems to enhancing the bioavailability and solubility of drug molecules.

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REFERENCES

1. Verma, S., Kaul, M., Rawat, A. and Saini, S., 2011. An overview on buccal drug delivery system. *International journal of pharmaceutical sciences and research*, 2(6), pp.1303-12.
2. Lou, J., Duan, H., Qin, Q., Teng, Z., Gan, F., Zhou, X. and Zhou, X., 2023. Advances in oral drug delivery systems: challenges and opportunities. *Pharmaceutics*, 15(2), p.484.
3. Shattat, G.F., 2015. A review article on hyperlipidemia: types, treatments and new drug targets. *Biomedical and pharmacology journal*, 7(1), pp.399-409.
4. Salekeen, R., Haider, A.N., Akhter, F., Billah, M.M., Islam, M.E. and Islam, K.M.D., 2022. Lipid oxidation in pathophysiology of atherosclerosis: Current understanding and therapeutic strategies. *International Journal of Cardiology Cardiovascular Risk and Prevention*, 14, pp.200143.
5. Nouh, F., Omar, M. and Younis, M., 2018. Risk factors and management of hyperlipidemia. *Asian journal of cardiology research*, 2(1), pp.1-10.
6. Al-ezzy, A.I.A. and Hameed, M.S., 2021. The physiological aspects of hyperlipidemia in health and disease. *Diyala Journal for veterinary sciences*, 1(2), pp 1-9.
7. Jia, Y., Zhang, Q., Zhang, Y., Wang, H., Niu, Q., Zhu, R., Li, J., Fan, W. and Zhang, Y., 2024. Effects of Polyphenol-Rich Foods on Lipids and Oxidative Stress Status in Patients with Hyperlipidemia: A Systematic Review of Randomized Controlled Trials. *Journal of Multidisciplinary Healthcare*, pp.3167-3179.
8. Stewart, J., Mccallin, T., Martinez, J., Chacko, S. and Yusuf, S., 2020. Hyperlipidemia. *Pediatrics in review*, 41(8), pp.393-402.
9. John, S.B. and Ayswarya, K., 2015. Formulation, optimization and evaluation of buccoadhesive delivery system of lovastatin. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*, pp.2256-2264.
10. Bhardwaj, P., Tripathi, P., Gupta, R. and Pandey, S., 2020. Niosomes: a review on niosomal research in the last decade. *Journal of drug delivery science and technology*, 56(A), pp.101581-88.
11. Rao, N.R., Shravani, B. and Reddy, M.S., 2013. Overview on buccal drug delivery systems. *Journal of pharmaceutical sciences and research*, 5(4), pp.80-91.
12. Mahboob, M.B.H., Riaz, T., Jamshaid, M., Bashir, I. and Zulfiqar, S., 2016. Oral films: A comprehensive review. *International Current Pharmaceutical Journal*, 5(12), pp.111-117.
13. Borbolla-Jiménez, F.V., Peña-Corona, S.I., Farah, S.J., Jiménez-Valdés, M.T., Pineda-Pérez, E., Romero-Montero, A., Del Prado-Audelo, M.L., Bernal-Chávez, S.A., Magaña, J.J. and Leyva-Gómez, G., 2023. Films for wound healing fabricated using a solvent casting technique. *Pharmaceutics*, 15(7), pp.1914-24.
14. Jagtap, V.D., 2020. Buccal Film—A Review on Novel Drug Delivery System. *Int. J. Res. Rev.*, 2(7), pp.17-28.
15. Kathe, K. and Kathpalia, H., 2017. Film forming systems for topical and transdermal drug delivery. *Asian journal of pharmaceutical sciences*, 12(6), pp.487-497
16. Prabhu, S.C., Parsekar, S.D., Shetty, A., Monteiro, S.S., Azharuddin, M. and Shabaraya, A.R., 2014. A review on fast dissolving sublingual films for systemic drug delivery. *Int J Pharm Chem Sci*, 3(2), pp.501-11
17. Raihan, R., Wafa, A., Zhakfar, A.M. and CK, S., 2024. Oral Disintegrating Films: A Review. *Journal of Natural Science Review*, 2(2), pp.60-74.
18. Bhardwaj, P., Tripathi, P., Gupta, R. and Pandey, S., 2020. Niosomes: a review on niosomal research in the last decade. *Journal of drug delivery science and technology*, 56(A), pp.101581-88.
19. Rodu, B. and Russell, C.M., 1988. Performance of a hydroxypropyl cellulose film former in normal and ulcerated oral mucosa. *Oral surgery, oral medicine, oral pathology*, 65(6), pp.699-703.
20. Badri S, Sailaja P, Annagowni Nr, Lunjala RS, Seshu D. 2022. A review on niosomes as novel drug delivery system. *International journal of indigenous herbs and drugs*. pp.29-87.
21. Alyami, H., Abdelaziz, K., Dahmash, E.Z. and Iyire, A., 2020. Nonionic surfactant vesicles (niosomes) for ocular drug delivery: Development, evaluation and toxicological profiling. *Journal of Drug Delivery Science and Technology*, 60, pp.10206-14

22. Sharma, R., Dua, J.S. and Parsad, D.N., 2022. An overview on niosomes: novel pharmaceutical drug delivery system. *Journal of drug delivery and therapeutics*, 12(2-s), pp.171-177.
23. Nti-Gyabaah, J., Chmielowski, R., Chan, V. and Chiew, Y.C., 2008. Solubility of lovastatin in a family of six alcohols: Ethanol, 1-propanol, 1-butanol, 1-pentanol, 1-hexanol, and 1-octanol. *International journal of pharmaceutics*, 359(1-2), pp.111-117.
24. Gunnam S, Nijhawan M, Aleti and Kamiseti.,2024. Formulation And Evaluation of Pulsatile Drug Delivery System of Lovastatin. *International Journal of Biology, pharmacy and Allied sciences*, 4(9), pp.2287-9
25. Gaber, D.A., 2020. Nanoparticles of lovastatin: design, optimization and in vivo evaluation. *International journal of nanomedicine*, pp.4225-4236.
26. Bhagat, A., Dangi, S.S., Ghatuary, S.K. and Parkhe, G., 2019. Formulation, development and evaluation of gastroretentive floating tablets of lovastatin using natural polymer. *EAS J Pharm Pharmacol*, 1(4), pp.92-8.
27. Bunaciu, A.A., Hoang, V.D. and Aboul-Enein, H.Y., 2025. Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy used in drug excipients compatibility studies. *Applied Spectroscopy Reviews*, 60(5), pp.385-403.
28. Thabet, Y., Elsabahy, M. and Eissa, N.G., 2022. Methods for preparation of niosomes: A focus on thin-film hydration method. *Methods*, 199, pp.9-15.
29. Alyami, H., Abdelaziz, K., Dahmash, E.Z. and Iyire, A., 2020. Nonionic surfactant vesicles (niosomes) for ocular drug delivery: Development, evaluation and toxicological profiling. *Journal of Drug Delivery Science and Technology*, 60, p.102069-8.
30. Zhang, W., Zhao, X., Yu, G. and Suo, M., 2021. Optimization of propofol loaded niosomal gel for transdermal delivery. *Journal of Biomaterials Science, Polymer Edition*, 32(7), pp.858-873.
31. Yaghoobian, M., Haeri, A., Bolourchian, N., Shahhosseni, S. and Dadashzadeh, S., 2020. The impact of surfactant composition and surface charge of niosomes on the oral absorption of repaglinide as a BCS II model drug. *International journal of nanomedicine*, pp.8767-8781.
32. Kate, N.S., Rane, B.R. and Jain, A.S., 2023. Development and evaluation of atorvastatin calcium nanovesicular niosomal gel for the treatment of periodontitis. *Engineering Proceedings*, 56(1), pp.66-74
33. Owodeha-Ashaka, K., Ilomuanya, M.O. and Iyire, A., 2021. Evaluation of sonication on stability-indicating properties of optimized pilocarpine hydrochloride-loaded niosomes in ocular drug delivery. *Progress in22 biomaterials*, 10, pp.207-220
34. Niaz, T. and Imran, M., 2021. Diffusion kinetics of nisin from composite coatings reinforced with nano-rhamnosomes. *Journal of Food Engineering*, 288, p.110143.
35. Sulthana, N. and Mohammed, S., 2019. Formulation and in vitro evaluation of oral disintegrating films of lovastatin. *IJPRHS*, 7(6), pp.3084-9.
36. Palepu, S., Sathyanarayana, T., Ravali, M., Dakshyani, P., Sirisha, U., Sri, P.D. and Srinu, M., 2019. Preparation and evaluation of fast dissolving sublingual film of lisinopril. *J. Drug Deliv. Ther.*, 17, pp.9-15
37. Mahajan, A., 2012. Formulation and evaluation of fast dissolving buccal films of sertraline. *Int J Drug Dev Res*, 4(1), pp.220-226.
38. Elagamy, H.I., Essa, E.A., Nouh, A. and El Maghraby, G.M., 2019. Development and evaluation of rapidly dissolving buccal films of naftopidil: in vitro and in vivo evaluation. *Drug development and industrial pharmacy*, 45(10), pp.1695-1706.
39. Zayed, G.M., Abd-El Rasoul, S., Ibrahim, M.A., Saddik, M.S. and Alshora, D.H., 2020. In vitro and in vivo characterization of domperidone-loaded fast dissolving buccal films. *Saudi pharmaceutical journal*, 28(3), pp.266-273.
40. Ansari, M., Sadarani, B. and Majumdar, A., 2018. Optimization and evaluation of mucoadhesive buccal films loaded with resveratrol. *Journal of Drug Delivery Science and Technology*, 44, pp.278-288.
41. Tejada, G., Barrera, M.G., Piccirilli, G.N., Sortino, M., Frattini, A., Salomón, C.J., Lamas, M.C. and Leonardi, D., 2017. Development and evaluation of buccal films based on chitosan for the potential treatment of oral candidiasis. *Aaps Pharmscitech*, 18, pp.936-946.
42. Ammar, H.O., Ghorab, M.M., Mahmoud, A.A. and Shahin, H.I., 2017. Design and in vitro/in vivo evaluation of ultra-thin mucoadhesive buccal film containing fluticasone propionate. *Aaps Pharmscitech*, 18, pp.93-103.
43. Dey, S.K., De, P.K., Sen, T., Shankar, V. and Banerjee, U., 2011. Formulation and in vitro evaluation of transdermal matrix patches of diclofenac sodium. *J Pharm Res*, 4(10), pp.3593-6.
44. Hanif, M., Zaman, M. and Chaurasiya, V., 2015. Polymers used in buccal film: a review. *Designed Monomers and Polymers*, 18(2), pp.105-111
45. Londhe, V.Y. and Umalkar, K.B., 2012. Formulation development and evaluation of fast dissolving film of telmisartan. *Indian Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 74(2), pp.122.
46. Adrover, A., Pedacchia, A., Petralito, S. and Spera, R., 2015. In vitro dissolution testing of oral thin films: A comparison between USP 1, USP 2 apparatuses and a new millifluidic flow-through device. *Chemical Engineering Research and Design*, 95, pp.173-178.
47. Gorle, A., Patil, P., Bhaskar, R. and Ola, M., 2015. Development and evaluation of buccal film containing antihypertensive agent. *The Pharma Innovation*, 4(1, Part B), pp.53-59.
48. Narayan, S. and Choudhary, M., 2017. A review on stability studies of pharmaceutical products. *International journal of applied pharmaceutical and biological research*, 2(3), pp.67-75